

Accelerating Offshore Renewable Energy - Trusted Data and Information Supply Chains Workshop Summary

ARDC Planet Research Data Commons
31 July 2024, Hobart and Online

Acknowledgments

Thank you to our many partners across research, government, industry and community including those who participated in this workshop. We would like to acknowledge the effort by the participants of IMAS, IMOS, UTas, WABSI and WAMSI in particular for assistance in compiling this report.

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Acknowledgement of Country

We acknowledge the traditional custodians throughout Australia and their continuing connection to, and deep knowledge of, the land and waters. We pay our respects to Elders both past and present.

Contributors

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1. Introduction

A workshop entitled ‘Accelerating Offshore Renewable Energy - Trusted Data and Information Supply Chains’ was hosted by the [ARDC’s Planet Research Data Commons](#), the [University of Tasmania’s Institute for Marine and Antarctic Studies](#) (IMAS), [NESP Marine and Coastal Hub](#), the [Integrated Marine Observing System](#) (IMOS), [Western Australian Biodiversity Science Institute](#) (WABSI) and [Western Australian Marine Science Institution](#) (WAMSI) at IMAS, Hobart on 31 July 2024.

The purpose of the workshop was to:

- introduce the ARDC’s Trusted Environmental Data And Information Supply Chains Program, and specifically the proposed Gippsland Offshore Renewable Energy Project, to research and data infrastructure leaders
- investigate research and government requirements for cumulative impact of offshore renewable energy
- and identify opportunities for partnerships.

Trusted Environmental Data And Information Supply Chains Program

[Offshore Infrastructure Regulator \(OIR\) guidance and regulation](#), The Planet RDC is working closely with Australian Government Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water (DCCEEW), national research infrastructures, state agencies, industry partners, Traditional Owners, universities, research institutions and researchers to establish ‘trusted data and information supply chains’ for priority regional use cases.

The [Independent Review of the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act](#) highlighted the need for an effective ‘supply chain’ of environmental information. The information required by researchers and decision-makers to understand the environment is obtained through a series of activities (see the [SAFE guide](#)). As with more traditional supply chains, each activity can be carried out by a different party, and coordination is needed for an efficient chain that delivers the right products at the right time to the right customers.

A trusted environmental data and information supply chain requires an effective system of data-sharing agreements and information systems that can talk with each other, and reliable data and analytics to produce information products that meet specific needs.

Three exemplar projects will create supply chains for regional use cases. These will be in regions of high biodiversity value, with different pressures on the environment and different groups of stakeholders.

Each exemplar project will establish:

- appropriate business and governance models

- data governance frameworks
- practices to make data and software/models FAIR
- stakeholder consensus on agreed standards and best practices for data, metadata, vocabularies, data exchange formats, quality, provenance, and trusted repositories
- reusable infrastructure solutions to enable data and model sharing and use to produce the required information and decision-support products¹.

Gippsland Offshore Renewable Energy Project

The emerging offshore renewable energy (ORE) sector in Australia presents exciting opportunities to meet increased energy demand and help drive the transition to renewable energy technologies. Assessing the potential environmental and social impacts presents a challenge due to the complex nature of cumulative impacts, and the need for ongoing environmental monitoring and adaptation.

The building of the infrastructure required to generate and transport wind energy, and the wind turbines themselves, can impact benthic (seabed) habitats, marine mammals such as whales, seabirds and migratory birds. There could also be social and economic impacts to fisheries. To fully understand and derive the cumulative impacts of multiple offshore wind farms, a quantitative assessment of environmental baselines, current state and pressures is required. Broad information required for this assessment includes:

- Pressures: sea surface temperature, fishing, seabed disturbance, pollution, noise, natural disasters, shipping, mining.
- Environmental baselines and current state: species abundance and distribution, habitat condition and extent, water quality.
- Impact: ecosystem services, fishing catch, economic assessments (degradation costs, economic benefit).

These data are collected by a wide range of stakeholders from research, government agencies and the offshore renewable energy industry sector.

The ARDC will invest \$1 million to establish data, analytics and governance infrastructure over a 2 year project, to support evidence-based environmental impact assessment for the Gippsland ORE declared area. This initial case study area will lay the foundation for the ultimate goal of scaling the technical and governance infrastructure nationally for all ORE areas.

This will require collaboration and governance from all research, government and industry sectors involved in offshore renewable energy.

¹ *Information product* refers to the object that is used by an end user that enables a manager or assessor to make a decision, for example a species distribution or groundwater map, spatial layers, Indigenous Knowledge story, or a decision-support tool. It could also be a model packaged with curated data that can be run and interpreted by a decision maker.

Co-design process

The ARDC is working with national leaders in marine research and data infrastructure (including the co-hosts of this workshop) to co-design the project. We are following the co-design process described in the [Planet Research Data Commons Co-Design Framework](#). The ARDC has completed the Problem Identification phase over several years of extensive consultation and information-gathering activities. We are now in the Project Shaping phase where we are holding workshops and discussions with interested parties to ensure the needs of regulators, researchers and industry are met.

These ARDC workshops follow on from 2 workshops facilitated by the NESP Marine and Coastal Hub that assembled the environmental knowledge base for threatened and migratory species relating to wind energy development in October 2023 and January 2024.

1. WORKSHOP OUTCOMES SUMMARY

The hybrid workshop had 42 participants from:

- ARDC
- Blue Economy CRC
- CSIRO
- DATA61
- DCCEEW - Environment Information Australia (EIA) and Nature Positive Regulation Division
- Geoscience Australia
- IMOS
- National Offshore Petroleum Safety & Environment Management Authority (NOPSEMA)
- University of Tasmania - IMAS
- WABSI
- WAMSI

A summary of key insights from the workshop is provided below, and more detailed summaries of the presentations and discussions are provided in [Appendix 1](#). The Agenda is attached in [Appendix 2](#).

Information needs for assessment of environmental impact of ORE

- ORE proponents require authoritative information on cumulative environmental impact to support licence applications and compliance with licence conditions and monitoring requirements.

- Government regulators require robust and reliable environmental information to support optimised decision making for delivery of national energy transition targets, and to assess the regional and cumulative impact of ORE development to enable nature positive.
- The Australian Government's [guidance on key environmental factors to be considered by ORE proponents in response to national environmental law](#) provides a framework for ORE information requirements.
- Other marine industries are developing environmental information products and there is an opportunity to achieve shared outcomes through cross-sector collaboration.
- Access to trusted and robust regional data is critical for improved and faster decision making by regulators.
- Time-critical decision-making needs (driven by national energy transition targets) place a high value on leveraging existing systems and proven approaches to streamlining data pipelines and information products. This includes pragmatic approaches to developing sound foundational data systems that can be continually improved with new science and technologies.
- To ensure the effectiveness of information products for regional use cases, developers should focus on creating solutions that are scalable and adaptable to accommodate a range of use cases and spatial contexts.

Trust and governance

- Governance to enable independent scientific endorsement of analytical methods, models and products is an essential requirement in delivering authoritative and recognised information products used for government and regulatory decision making processes.
- Regional shared models provide a process to drive model development and innovation to increase confidence in the information product outputs. These combined attributes provide a lower risk environment for industry to develop proposals for approval, fast track the production of trusted information and support improved evidence based decision making.
- Governments are recognising the importance of FAIR data and independent, trusted and authoritative information through development of new guidelines and legislative frameworks.
- Enduring industry, research and government partnerships are needed to create a collaborative and unified approach to the development of recognised information products derived from trusted data supply chains.
- Industry relationships and collaboration is fundamental to success for all stakeholders in the development of ORE. Industry is generally open to collaboration with the research and science sector around shared analytics because it generates trusted information for their development proposals, reducing the risk of proposal legal challenges, and improving social licence.

Infrastructure and system requirements

- A successful shared data and information system is networked by design and is supported by a sustainable business model.
- Systems need to provide appropriate mechanisms to meet the data security requirements and access and usage conditions of data providers.
- A scalable and adaptable technology model is required to meet a wide range of environmental assessment use cases.
- A scalable and adaptable ORE data and information model will lend itself to wider application for a range of regional and industry contexts.
- Government and regulator personnel require an intuitive, effective and reliable interface to access environmental information products that support assessment, approval, monitoring and reporting processes.
- System architecture should support the implementation of the FAIR data principles.
- Development and maintenance costs are important considerations in developing a sustainable regional shared data and information solution.

Data and information gaps

- Most existing approaches to impact assessment are qualitative, or semi-qualitative, but there is a growing requirement for quantitative and cumulative based impact assessment.
- Development of cumulative impact models with appropriate resolution has begun but there are complex challenges in the integration of multiple pressure, spatial and temporal variables.
- Collaborating with industry to access their data will augment research data resources and support the development of high-value model outputs.
- Existing gaps in environmental values information required for impact assessment includes the lack of accessible bird and cetacean data.

APPENDIX 1. WORKSHOP DISCUSSION DETAILS

Overview of existing relevant initiatives and infrastructures

- [Shared Environmental Analytics Facility \(SEAF\)](#)
 - SEAF is a mechanism for securely sharing and interpreting environmental data. It enables a trusted data and information supply chain that generates information products, like maps, reports and forecasting tools for use in research and decision making.
 - SEAF is a collective effort between research, government and industry, providing trusted, single-point access to disparate information sources.
 - Industry collects and holds a significant amount of environmental data.
 - It uses shared data in predictive models and analytics – turning it into practical, usable information and forecasting tools, enabling users to make more informed decisions for cumulative environmental impact assessments, at a region-specific scale.
 - It is extensible to any region or application.
- [SEAF for Cockburn Sound](#) case study
 - Western Australia’s Cockburn Sound supports vital industrial complexes, trade networks, water and wastewater utilities. The marine systems are highly valued by the community for recreation and tourism and have cultural significance for Traditional Owners. Industrial operations and ecosystem resilience are at risk from climate change, economic and social change.
 - The Cockburn Sound SEAF spoke delivers hydrodynamic and sediment transport models and maps, integrated marine ecosystem biogeochemistry and ecological models and maps and information towards the Cockburn Sound DPSIR reporting model. These will enable more informed decision making for industry, government and regulators.
- [Integrated Marine Observing System](#) (IMOS) and [Australian Ocean Data Network](#) (AODN)
 - IMOS operates a wide range of [observing equipment](#) throughout Australia’s coastal and open ocean estate. IMOS makes all of its quality controlled data openly and freely accessible via the AODN data repository. The AODN is an IODE National Oceanographic Data Centre (NODC) accredited and Core Trust Seal certified data repository and is an essential function within IMOS.
 - IMOS follows internationally recognised data collection protocols, ensuring that measurements (e.g., temperature, salinity, currents) are collected consistently across different platforms and instruments (e.g., moorings, gliders, buoys). The data undergo quality control processes that are based on internationally accepted guidelines such as

those from the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). The data collection protocols are peer reviewed and published in the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS).

- The AODN maintains a growing national catalogue of over 14,500 marine datasets and a data Portal with over 300 well-curated dataset collections contributed by 18 partner organisations including IMOS, IMAS and NESP Marine and Coastal Hub data.
 - The IMOS / AODN adheres to a range of international and national data standards to ensure that marine and oceanographic data is discoverable, accessible, and interoperable. These standards help maintain data quality, consistency, and usability across a wide range of datasets. They include ISO 19115 Metadata Standard, Climate and Forecast (CF) Conventions and OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) Standards (GIS standards).
 - AODN uses a data lake like architecture with data stored predominately in NetCDF array based formats. Data is provided through various access options.
 - THREDDS data provisioning - good for models
 - OGC compliant web services - GIS and web-map compatible
 - Cloud optimised formats - big data, data science and AI/ML friendly
 - IMOS and AODN are connected to the international community
- [NESP Marine and Coastal Hub](#) research activity overview
 - [Project 3.21](#) - Identifying priority datasets for the Gippsland declaration area and pathways for their use in decision-making
 - This project identified information, data and data products outside the public domain through a broad-scale inventory process.
 - [Project 3.3](#) - Guiding the sustainable development of offshore renewables and other emerging marine industries in Australia
 - This project established an inventory of existing environmental and cultural data and best-practice monitoring standards to support regulatory decision-making.
 - [Project 4.7](#) - Development of regional modelling and risk assessments to inform offshore renewable decision-making
 - This project will demonstrate the use of two kinds of modelling (whole-of-ecosystem modelling and individual species modelling) to estimate the impacts and risks of installing ORE infrastructure in the Gippsland declared region. (see details in [Research advances](#) section, Appendix 1).
 - [Project 4.9](#) - Assessing the vulnerability of southern right whale and blue whale populations to disturbance from windfarm developments.
 - This desktop study will use available data and expert opinion to develop interim Population Consequences of Disturbance (PCoD) models for blue whales and southern right whales in relation to one or multiple offshore wind farm developments off Portland and Gippsland, Victoria.

- [Blue Economy CRC](#)
 - The Blue Economy CRC undertakes industry focused research and training to support the growth of the Blue Economy with a focus on: offshore aquaculture and renewable energy production.
 - Strong engagement with industry. Wind farm companies are stakeholders on current projects.

- [Seamap Australia](#) from [Institute of Marine and Antarctic Studies](#) (IMAS)
 - Seamap Australia is the national repository for the collection of marine benthic habitat datasets. It began in 2017 and is maintained in the national interest by IMAS and the University of Tasmania. Its expansion relies on the maturation of other national data infrastructures
 - The Seamap Australia portal provides a single point of access to nationally aggregated, uniformly classified marine habitat spatial data through standards-based data services.
 - The hierarchical habitat classification scheme used by Seamap in the National Benthic Habitat Layer can accommodate any schema/classifications of source habitat datasets, whilst preserving the original (source) classification to allow full backwards-engineering. Additionally, annotation services like Squidle+ have built-in semantic translations that enable cross-walking between different schemes (eg CATAMI, Aus Morphospecies Catalogue, WORMS)
 - Seamap Australia use the IMAS Data Repository for all data operations. Based on the AODN software infrastructure, it supports database and file based storage, THREDDS and OGC compliant web services and a metadata catalogue with IOS19115 compliant metadata.

- **“State of Knowledge” tool for Parks Australia** built on existing Seamap capabilities - Peter
 - State of knowledge reporting tool indexes information on research effort and data availability “on the fly” for key national data streams (thematic repositories)
 - Summary stats break down research effort by relevant attributes - e.g. gridded bathymetry resolution, methods of imagery collection, public vs private status of data, date ranges, etc. Includes links to where you would access that data.
 - Metadata on research effort is derived from OGC Web Services provided by thematic data aggregators: Squidle+, MARS sediment database, AusSeabed, GlobalArchive
 - Printable region report pages for Australian Marine Parks provide widgets based on these data streams

- This project provides a model for defining data needs for information products to address specific user questions
 - Were able to do this because Parks Australia defined 6 questions that we could investigate the data needs for
- [AusSeabed](#) and [Geoscience Australia](#)
 - AusSeabed currently contains bathymetry data, but backscatter, seismic, sub-seafloor, sediment, etc on the roadmap. Data comes from government, industry and research.
 - GA now has a mandate to map the seafloor, and a modest amount of money for collating existing multibeam data to produce maps (30m resolution)
 - AusSeabed can be used for planning for survey activities. Users can share survey plans, and submit a request to HIP for their area of interest.
 - Hydrographic Information Panel (HIP) - ~9 private companies that do the surveying, directed by the Australian Hydrographic Office (AHO) - everything that comes out of HIP goes on AusSeabed
 - The producers of the data (hydrographers/ocean surveyors) are more engaged than the data owners (oil and gas companies)
 - Also looking to display coverage of AHO surveys (but not actual AHO data)
 - GA build information products from the AusSeabed data, producing seabed geomorphology maps

Stakeholder needs for shared environmental data and analytics in the development of offshore renewable energy

Discussion

Research requirements

- Research organisations engaging with industry are hearing about demand for authoritative information on cumulative environmental impact to support licence applications and approval processes. International experience and government requirements are important in informing suitable approaches to data and information frameworks for ORE.

Government requirements

- National regulatory systems require regional approaches to the assembly of all relevant data to support decision making. Access to trusted and robust data is critical to improved and faster decision making.
- Need to harness all available data to make decisions. EIA is working on it but doesn't currently have regional data to allow cumulative assessment.
- Urgency for this work is being driven by national energy transition targets.
- The assembly of all available environmental data (including proponent data) is important to the establishment of environmental baselines that are required to understand impacts, trends, the efficacy of management measures, and inform adaptive management processes.
- WAMSI and ARDC have invested heavily in SEAF and been productive in creating an analytic framework for WA regulatory purposes, and there is the potential for leveraging this for DCCEEW's needs in servicing the energy transition.
- DCCEEW-EIA are a primary end user, and are keen to be involved from inception of the program and be embedded in the steering structure.
- Given the ambitious timelines we can't focus on delivering a gold standard solution right now. It should be an iterative process with continuous improvement at the heart. We need to get the basics right but then continue to develop the products.
- There is a keen interest from NPRD in leveraging existing data systems and information products from a regulatory perspective, and other divisions also have strong interest e.g. biodiversity, regional planning, sustainable oceans team. NPRD has significant funding for a range of research projects.
- Government is developing legislation for a statutory Head of EIA who will be responsible for providing trusted and authoritative information to the public, EPA and Minister. This is being underpinned by the development of government data standard guidelines. There is a role for EIA

to play in identifying and pointing to trusted and authoritative data, and providing governance structures where they do not currently exist.

SEAF approach to enabling trusted information supply chains

SEAF logic - Luke Twomey, WAMSI

- The products required for assessing a proposal (decision-making tools, maps, spatial layers, etc) are determined by the regulators, proponents and industry
- Those products are produced by trusted research partners
- The products are endorsed as fit-for-purpose by the governing body of the regional SEAF (comprised of the SEAF partners)
- This includes endorsing standards and protocols for the data and information supply chain (i.e.. data collection, data processing, and models and analytics)
- For ORE, much of this may be done by the National Marine Science Committee (NMSC) - which is a trusted science body and has the capacity to reach out to the network of marine scientists to recommend and develop standards and research.
- Data collection and model development work is directed by the required tools, and is conducted in a coordinated manner.
- Initially products can be the best currently available, and can (and should) be iteratively improved over time. The focus of SEAF can also expand to include other sectors and uses for the region (i.e. fisheries, environmental economic accounting, etc).

Discussion and questions

Trust and Confidence

- An authoritative scientific framework is needed to oversee the development and use of fit for purpose analytics and models recognised by regulators and assessment authorities.
 - Agreed, however the recognition and codification of required models and information products used to support decision making is evolving.
- Confidence in the models used to develop information products is an important factor in the regulatory decision making process. How do we build trust in, and manage uncertainty in the model(s), particularly when there are so many data gaps?
 - The SEAF approach enables regional experts from research to develop models for a region, with industry and regulators providing feedback for continual improvement. This is a better approach than the current situation where industry consultants use their own models.
 - SEAF does not propose 'one model to rule them all' - industry may tweak the model using shared data, but ideally this would go back into the shared model.

- What is the most appropriate data system that can:
 - Deliver the various security needs of data providers
 - Enable access to the secure combined data pool for analytics and modelling.
 - Establish trust in the data used and information product output

SEAF technical/operation questions

- What scale of resources are required to develop and operate data pipelines and analytical systems such as those outlined?
 - Setting up the technical system for a SEAF spoke could be done rapidly, within weeks. The data and analytical pipelines depend on the regional use case.
- Are there any constraints in contributing data to shared analytical systems?
 - No. It's important to make it as easy as possible for people to contribute data, and the data engineering function drives the quality of the data going in.
- How do shared analytic systems manage commercially or other forms of sensitive data?
 - SEAF used a zoned approach (private, collaborative, public zones), data encryption, and distributed analytics. Data owners select which zone the data is housed in and how their data moves through the system. For example, in the Pilbara SEAF, BHP and Rio Tinto contribute commercially sensitive groundwater data to their own private zones, and the shared groundwater model accesses the encrypted data, and only the model output is shared.
- How does the data access control work in SEAF?
 - Data security and access controls are core to the design of SEAF - built in access controls include data encryption, and can deal with sharing requirements at various project stages. Legislation drives when industry information has to be released.
- If an agency was involved in more than one regional SEAF, do they have to engage with each one separately?
 - This could be managed at Hub level

Industry response to SEAF approach, and needs

- How is industry responding to shared data approaches such as SEAF?
 - Industry has a number of challenges to manage including risk, costs, trust, information equality and social licence which shared data and information approaches can help address. Industry is attracted to solutions that can minimise approval timelines, reduce approval uncertainty, and reduce approval conditions.
 - Legal challenges to development applications slow them down. Shared analytics with authoritative data, and authoritative scientific guidance, helps optimise getting the proposal to the assessment stage, and minimises the risk of appeal.
 - Social licence is a real driver for industry.

- Acceleration of approvals leads to huge economic benefits.
- Being able to provide industry with environmental information upfront, saving them from doing it is attractive to industry.
 - Companies in Europe expect governments to provide a certain amount of environmental data, but the Australian marine estate is so large it is hard for governments here.
 - We're looking at this for national marine seafloor mapping (funding for collating using existing data only).
 - WAMSI is proposing a government-funded science program for ORE in WA.
- Industry want, and are open to collaboration, they want to be a trusted partner with government and research. All the elements exist (e.g. governance, confidentiality, etc) - but relationship with industry is critical.
- Industry needs credible information to de-risk at all phases of ORE development - they need to know what the effects will be of vessels, floating cables, electromagnetic fields around cables, turbines, etc. Decisions also need to be made around social, cultural, and economic aspects. Partnerships are required for this.
- Tourism, oil, gas, aquaculture industries all need much of the same information.
- There are examples from overseas, e.g. NOAA and Norstead in the US - we should look at these data sharing agreements as a precedent.
- Industry rely on consultants, e.g. RPS, BMT - will consultants engage with us?
 - Cockburn Sound is bringing in BMT, and conversations with RPS are being had by WAMSI and NESP MaC Hub.
- Are there other sectors that could benefit from this [SEAF] framework? For example NOPSEMA regulates oil and gas industries, and there are fisheries and aquaculture.
 - SEAF was designed to be adapted and adopted over time. The SEAF in Cockburn Sound has already been redeployed to be used by WaterCorp for algal blooms.
 - Blue Economy CRC are successfully working with the fisheries industry on data sharing programs to generate spatial products and are interested in participating in the ORE program.

Research advances

Development of regional modelling and risk assessments to inform offshore renewable decision-making (NESP Marine and Coastal Hub [Project 4.7](#)) - Keith Hayes, CSIRO

- Started May 2024, runs until April 2027
- Understanding of regional cumulative impact is an important information requirement in environmental impact assessment and approval processes. Current approaches to cumulative impact assessment are generally qualitative or semi-qualitative.
- The models needed are not codified yet, that space is evolving.
- This project will use whole-of-ecosystem modelling and individual species modelling to estimate the impacts and risks of installing ORE infrastructure in the [Gippsland declared region](#). The project will use the [Impact pathways](#) defined by DCCEEW to structure its approach and methods, and will work with DCCEEW and NOPSEMA to identify priority species and associated data needs.
- Population models will be developed for key threatened and migratory species.
- A whole-of-ecosystem approach will be used to assess the physical effects of wind farms on hydrodynamics and sediment transport (seabed disturbance and loss of/harm to benthic habitats) and the multiple pathways leading to possible impacts on Australian Marine Parks.
- New or existing regional-scale hydrodynamic models will be used to parameterise the physical components of a whole-of-ecosystem model such as Atlantis
- Industry collected bird and cetacean data from feasibility studies “will be gold” - the models can be built without it, but will be a lot better with it.

Where are the gaps in assessing cumulative impact and operationalising a trusted data supply chain for government and industry?

Discussion summary

Government regulator needs

- The Australian Government is looking to engage with industry, research and state government around data and information needs. There is a need to understand available capacity for development of analytical tools that meet national assessment and regulation needs.

- A simple and practical process is required for accessing data and information that can be used by regulatory assessment staff and industry for environmental assessment, approval, monitoring and adaptive management.
 - Industry data needs to be curated and managed by competent data managers and securely stored for future access.
 - One data submission point for proponents is the goal, however, given the size of the data, how this will be stored and managed over time is a key challenge.
- A research investment portfolio from DCCEEW NPRD regarding environmental aspects of ORE will be released in the near future.
 - Keen to have this data brought together to make sure it can be used, and that the data is delivering outcomes that are practical and can be built on over time.
 - Government is not able to deliver on all data gaps. We need to identify the critical gaps and look at how proponent data can support this.
- The issues are fast evolving and the Australian environmental context is unique - we need the ability to understand where changes [to environmental approval conditions] need to be made, and to pick up rapid declines in species early to manage them.
- Working with key experts is important for quality assurance, including independent review
- Data and information systems need to address requirements for the national ORE program that can also have application for terrestrial environmental assessments.
- Systems need to be developed around agreed data standards through recognised data repositories with suitable access control systems, and assessment officers need access to these so they have the data needed to make decisions.
- Knowledge of data gaps is an important starting point.
- Trusted information is required to demonstrate that industry operations will comply with environmental controls and conditions.
- It's difficult for regulators to co-ordinate and be aware of all the research that is going on. Visibility of research activity is important for improved coordination of effort, avoidance of duplicated effort and the identification of priorities for investment.
 - This is also an issue for consultants.
- There are national priorities to optimise approval processes, reduce costs and minimise risk. The focus for the government is moving to understanding and assessing regional cumulative impacts.
- Cumulative impact assessment involves challenging complexity and it is therefore important to develop CIA through a staged approach using currently available data.
- The development of robust data and information systems has an important role in addressing misinformation issues.

Research needs

- Data and models for quantitative assessment of cumulative environmental impact are needed to support decision making at regional scales
- Building relationships with government and industry is important to facilitate research translation including - information sharing, trust, shared goal setting and clear understanding of information requirements
- Clarification of roles for research stakeholders in the program is important in the development and operation of a coordinated and unified shared data and analytics model for ORE. This program can be used to develop shared objectives and purpose across the marine research sector.
- There are some clear gaps in regionally specific data on birds and cetaceans that will be required for understanding of ORE environmental impacts.
- We are working on how we define cumulative impact - what are the boundaries we put around this? What species, how many? Also need to include multiple pressures (not just ORE) and cumulative impacts on environmental value other than species.
 - As you add species and values the data needs expand, so scoping of what is adequate is required.
- A successful shared data and information program has a process that is networked by design with a business model to deliver a sustainable service.
- A new shared data and analytics program for ORE can take advantage of the extensive existing system of marine research, data assets and technology.
- Gippsland ORE is a focus for development of processes and information products that will have national application for multiple users. Most information product requirements for assessment and approvals can be identified but an appropriate standard that will deliver faster decisions is to be defined.
- Quality and provenance -
 - Where your derived products need iterative data cleaning and reprocessing you need full traceability back to original raw data. If you are planning on keeping raw data private, you won't be able to do that (without automated QA/QC)

Links shared by participants

[Key environmental factors for offshore windfarm environmental impact assessment under the EPBC Act 1999 \(dcceew.gov.au\)](https://www.dcceew.gov.au)

[Assessing and Managing Impacts to Underwater Cultural Heritage in Australian Waters - DCCEEW](#)

Closing comments – how do we want to work together to enable this vision?

- It's important for the research community, through national marine science plans, to communicate the science required for management of marine environments and minimising development impacts as well as understand the needs of policy and regulation. Look to develop mechanisms to build communication between stakeholders in order to close information loops.
- There are existing examples of other substantial efforts on FAIR data approaches for areas such as climate change and fisheries. This project can be another exemplar of this model through a focus on birds and mammals.
- Cultural and social aspects are important elements of a whole of environment approach for all industries operating in the marine environment.
- Next steps will need to include summaries of engagement activities, program development roadmap, program governance structure planning and development of the partner consortium with clarification of roles and responsibilities.
- The proposed funding model is a minimum 1:1 cash and/or in-kind co-investment from partners (combined) to match ARDC's proposed contribution of \$1M.

Next steps

- Targeted ORE industry engagement to explore collaboration opportunities and data and information requirements
- Follow up sessions with stakeholders and program partners
- Co-development of the ORE TEDISC roadmap and associated work packages
- The ARDC will work with partners to develop and socialise a project plan by 30 November 2024.

APPENDIX 2 - AGENDA

1. Welcome and introductions (Nicole Webster, IMAS)
2. Introduction to ARDC's trusted environmental data and information supply chains program (Hamish Holewa, ARDC)
3. The need for shared environmental analytics in offshore renewable energy for government, industry and research
 - a. Overview of successful Public-Private Partnership - Shared Environmental Analytics Facility (SEAF) for Cockburn Sound (Luke Twomey, WAMSI)
 - b. Existing data infrastructures, standards and protocols (Mark Rehbein, IMOS)
 - c. Defining the need from a research perspective and overview of relevant major research programs (Alan Jordan, NESP Marine and Coastal Hub)
 - d. Regulator perspective (Chris Hicks, Nature Positive Regulation Division DCCEEW)
4. Co-design process and desired outcomes for the ARDC Offshore Renewable Energy trusted data and information supply chain project (Kerry Levett, ARDC)
5. SEAF logic (Luke Twomey, WAMSI)
6. Group discussion
7. Relevant research advances and work already undertaken, and existing data infrastructure
 - a. NESP Marine and Coastal Hub Project 4.7 (Keith Hayes, CSIRO)
 - b. SeaMap Australia (Emma Flukes, IMAS)
 - c. 'State of Knowledge' tool for Parks Australia (Emma Flukes, IMAS)
8. Stakeholder needs and benefits of a research-government-industry partnership
 - a. What does success look like for each sector?
9. Where are the gaps in assessing cumulative impact and operationalising a trusted data supply chain for government and industry?
10. Summary and next steps – how do we want to work together to enable this vision?

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